

1 MEASURES

Worrying. The German version of the Penn State Worry Questionnaire (PSWQ-d; [7]) assesses trait worrying as the major component of Generalized Anxiety Disorder based on the criteria stated in DSM-III-R. It includes 16 items (e.g. “My worries overwhelm me”), five of which are reverse coded. The items are scored on a 5-point Likert-scale ranging from ‘not at all typical of me’ to ‘very typical of me’. A total sum score captures the overall tendency to worry. The scale shows factorial validity and an internal consistency of $\alpha = .95$ in the present sample [4, 7].

Intolerance of Uncertainty. The German version of the Intolerance of Uncertainty Scale (IUS; [3]) was adapted from Freeston et al. [2]. It consists of 18 items (e.g. “Unforeseen events upset me greatly”) in three subscales on a 5-point Likert-scale ranging from ‘not at all typical of me’ to ‘very typical of me’. Intolerance of Uncertainty is assessed as the total sum score. Factorial validity is reported and the present sample presents an internal consistency of $\alpha = .94$ [3].

Website content. The Web-CLIC (Website—Clarity, Likeability, Informativeness, and Credibility; [11]) assesses the user’s subjective perception of website content perception. This questionnaire consists of twelve items on four subscales representing the general factor ‘subjective perception of content’ (e.g. “The texts provide me information in a clear and concise manner”). It is captured as the average value. The questionnaire has been shown to possess strong construct validity and an internal consistency of $\alpha = .95$ in this sample [11].

Website usability. To measure subjective usability, the a scale proposed by Flavián et al. [1], translated in Thielsch [8] and adapted by Thielsch et al. [10] was used that consists of seven items (e.g. “It is easy to navigate within this website.”). It is captured as the average value. The usability scale shows factorial validity and presents an internal consistency of $\alpha = .96$ in this sample [8].

Website aesthetics. The short version of the Visual Aesthetics of Websites Inventory VisAWI (VisAWI-S; [6]) assesses the users perception of the website’s aesthetic impression. It contains four items (e.g. “The colour composition is attractive.”) and shows good reliability and construct validity [6]. The present sample presents an internal consistency of $\alpha = .91$.

Behavior intention. The intention to revisit as an overall measure of appreciation, was captured using three items (e.g. “I will visit the website on a regular basis.”). The internal consistency in these three items in the present sample is $\alpha = .88$. Additionally, one item evaluates the intention to recommend a website (“I would recommend this website to friends and acquaintances.”). Similarly to Thielsch and Thielsch’s [12] methodology, the items were taken from Moshagen and Thielsch [5] and aggregated as proposed by Thielsch et al. [9].

2 PROCEDURE AND STIMULUS MATERIAL

The present dataset consists of two surveys. Survey 1 was conducted in July 2018 and Survey 2 was conducted in April and May 2018 via QuestBack on its academic platform Unipark.

Survey 1. After opening the study website, participants were provided with information on the study’s goals and further procedure. After giving their consent to participate, participants entered their demographic data and proceeded to fill out the questionnaires screening their worrying tendencies and related constructs as described under measures. After finishing, participants were given the opportunity to withdraw their data and, if wanted, received feedback on their worrying tendencies as well as resources to educate oneself. The median time to complete the task was 11:08 minutes.

Survey 2. Opening the study website, participants were instructed in terms of goals and further procedure as well as a possibility to win a voucher of 50€ for an online-bookstore or credit for psychology students. After giving information on their demographic background and internet usage habits, participants were assigned one of ten websites randomly. They were asked to browse that website, state whether they knew it beforehand and evaluate it with the tools described under measures. The median time to complete this task was 7:35 minutes.

3 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

For the statistical analysis, we used RStudio (Version 1.2.5019) to analyze the descriptive data and conduct a structure equation model with the package “lavaan”. In addition to the standard packages installed with RStudio, the package “car” recoded the items and “psych” helped analyze the questionnaires internal consistency. All variables were group mean centered. To assess the fit of the calculated structure equation model, the chi-squared test, RMSEA, CFI, TLI and SRMR were computed.

The present sample has been recruited via the online panel Psyweb and scores from the two surveys investigated were matched with the participants’ Psyweb ID. In 15 cases, two sets of answers were given with the same Psyweb ID. These were excluded from the analysis. Out 541 participants, 8 did not give consent to work with their data in one of the two surveys and 127 stopped filling out at least one of the two surveys and were therefore excluded. Dropouts did not differ in age from the examined sample but included relatively more female than male participants. In ten cases, answers to the questionnaire on worrying were not given and in one case, a participant did not state an identification with the binary gender construct. While acknowledging the freedom not to answer certain questions, these participants were excluded from the analysis because not all of the scores included in the structure equation model were given in these observations.

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